

Center for Composite Materials

Forming with Partially Cured TuFF/Thermoset Prepregs

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TuFF: Tailored Universal Feedstock for Forming

- **Chopped fibers** are highly **aligned** by water flow onto thin film
- Films of aligned fiber are prepregged with resin
- Prepreg can be used in **thermoforming process**
 - **Allows for stretch** during forming
 - Final properties comparable to continuous unidirectional prepreg

Outline

Process Development

Outline

Process Development

Problem Motivation

- Is it possible to implement progressive forming with TuFF/**thermoset** prepreg?
- Challenges
 - Thermoset low viscosity at temperature leads to resin bleed
 - Requires curing to hold structure between forming steps
 - Limited working time

Thermoplastic Forming

Outline

Process Development

Partial Curing of TuFF/977-3

PROCESS METHODOLOGY

Traditional Forming with Thermosets

- Why Thermosets?
 - Durable
 - Heat resistant

Forming + Part Ejection above T_g

Proposed Solution

Stage Resin

Pre-form blank

Final Form + Cure

Benefits:

1. Reduces TuFF/977-3 porosity issues:
 - a. Vent volatiles with oven-vacuum (no pressure and no bleed)
 - b. Reduces resin bleed during cure (higher visc. and shorter time to gel)
2. Reduces risk:
 - a. Inspect after preforming (visual)
 - b. Splitting the forming process: deep draw vs detailed feature
3. Reduces cycle time:
 - a. Stamping press at constant temp.
 - b. Parallel processes

Proposed Solution

⇒ Partially Cure w/ Oven

Pre-form blank

Final Form + Cure

Proposed Solution

Stage Resin

Pre-form blank

⇒ Deep Draw (Coarse Features)

Final Form + Cure

Proposed Solution

Stage Resin

Pre-form blank

Deep Draw (Coarse Features)
(At Temperature)

Final Form
+ Cure

Proposed Solution

Stage Resin

Pre-form blank

⇒ Deep Draw (Coarse Features)

⇒ Visual Inspection of Parts

Final Form + Cure

Proposed Solution

Stage Resin

Pre-form blank

Final Form + Cure

⇒ Final Forming + Curing in Batch Process

Proposed Solution

Part Production Quality

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Part Production Speed

3. Reduces cycle time:

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Outline

Process Development

Rheo-Cure Behavior

PROCESS MODELING

Modeling Resin Behavior

Modeling Resin Behavior

Modeling Degree of Cure

- Experimental Runs on DSC
 - Isothermal hold 140-200C (30hr)
 - 4 Trials at each temperature
- Simple Model Fit
 - High accuracy desired for $\alpha \leq 0.4$
 - Optimization script used for fitting

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = K_1(1 - \alpha)^{n_1} + K_2\alpha^m(1 - \alpha)^{n_2}$$

$$k = A \cdot e^{-\frac{Ea}{RT}}$$

Cure Kinetics Model

Glass Transition/Cure Relationship

Process Model

Start with:

$T_g > 25^\circ\text{C}$

$\alpha < \alpha_{\text{gel}}$

$15\% < \alpha < 38\%$

Choose $\alpha = 20\%$

Define viscosity targets

Obtain temperature/strain rate

Extension Test Forming Window

Outline

Process Development

Material Characterization w/ Partial Cure Process

MECHANICAL TESTING RESULTS

Comparing Processes

Main Questions:

- *Can we accurately model the partial curing process?*
- *Does processing method affect material quality?*

Fabricating Panels

Fabricating Panels

Resin Bleed Out

1. Staged
 $\alpha_0 = 20\%$
 $T_g = 35^\circ\text{C}$

2. Control
 $\alpha_0 = 0\%$
 $T_g = -3^\circ\text{C}$

	Mass Difference (g)	
	Staged	Control
Panel	- 1.0	- 6.0
Breather	+ 1.1	+ 6.4
% Mass Loss	-1.5%	-8.8%

C-SCAN

Porosity from resin bleed out

1. Staged

2. Control

Uniaxial Tension Test Results

- ASTM D3039 standard used
- $[0]_4$ Layup
- 7 samples from each panel (14 total samples tested)

	Failure Strength (ksi)	Failure Strain (%)	Modulus (Msi)
Control Panel	260 \pm 34.6	1.13 \pm 0.21	21.5 \pm 0.23
Staged Panel	287 \pm 15.1	1.38 \pm 0.07	19.8 \pm 0.14
Previous Work	290 \pm 16.8	1.31 \pm 0.07	21.3 \pm 0.08

Extension Testing w/ Partial Cure Material

DEFORMATION CHARACTERISTICS

Model Development Framework

Model Development Framework

Defining a New Forming Window

Estimating Temperature/Viscosity Relationships

- Initial Estimation:
 - Polymer viscosity curves used to guess forming window for partial cure material
 - Provides a starting point for testing

Estimating Temperature/Viscosity Relationships

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 - Polymer viscosity curves used to guess forming window for partial cure material
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Estimating Temperature/Viscosity Relationships

- Initial Estimation:
 - Polymer viscosity (n_p) used to guess forming window for partial cure material
 - Provides a starting point for testing

Measured via Instron Testing

$$\left\{ \frac{\sigma}{\dot{\epsilon}} = n_p \cdot c \right.$$

Apparent Viscosity (η_L)

Forming Process Window Development

- Objective:
 - Identify ideal forming temperatures
- Method:
 - Extension Test (1" wide samples)
 - Digital Image Correlation (DIC) for strain limit calculation
- Procedure:
 - Stretch 25.4×90 mm partially cured sample
 - Fixed $\dot{\epsilon}$ (s^{-1}) and T ($^{\circ}C$)

Test setup: a sample is gripped and stretched inside an environment chamber

Data analysis: Digital image correlation (DIC) tracks local strains over time.

Force is measured by a load cell to calculate stress (not shown)

Forming Improvements of Partially Cured Blanks

- Observed Differences (Visual)
 - Staged samples exhibit:
 - Greater uniformity and necking
 - Failure typically in center 1/3
 - Almost all samples remained intact
- Potential Reasons:
 - Partial cure = Longer polymer chains
 - Increases viscous length scale → better stability

Forming Process Window (Staged)

Forming Rate of 0.01 s^{-1}

- B-staged prepreg (uncured) showed maximum formability at 60C
- Increasing the cure to 20% (staged) showed maximum formability at 110C

Anticipate forming window increase of +20°C for every x10 increase in $\dot{\epsilon}$

Forming Window Temperatures (°C)		
Strain Rate	$\alpha = 0\%$	$\alpha = 20\%$
0.001	40	90
0.01	60	110
0.1	80	130

Extension Test Results (Staged)

Strain Rate = 0.01 /s

Strain Rate = 0.1 /s

Summary

- **Developed** a process for rapid manufacturing of TuFF/977-3
 - Increase cure to 20% (cure cycle/model dev.)
 - Rapid Stamp/Eject (forming process window shift)
- **Demonstrated:** Accurate cure kinetics below 40% cure
- **Demonstrated:** Reduced resin bleed out during curing of staged material
- **Demonstrated:** Tensile properties of staged blanks
- **Demonstrated:** Extension characteristics of staged blanks

Summary

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Path Forward:

- *Application to Forming*
 - *Form Complex Geometries*
 - *AniForm Modeling of Interface*